

Federation of Service Catalogues, based on IDS and Gaia-X Self-Descriptions

A Proof of Concept and governance aspects realized for the ZeroW Data Space

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the design and implementation of a Service Catalogue in a federated and open data infrastructure. The design of the Service Catalogue is compliant with the Gaia-X Trust Framework, the DSSC Blueprint, the IDSA Reference architecture version 4.0 and includes the use of Self Sovereign Identities and Self descriptions to increase trust and semantic interoperability, respectively. Working proof of concepts of the Service Catalogue were demonstrated during Hackathons in Bilbao and subsequently implemented as part of the ZeroW dataspace. Although the main focus of this paper is technical- and semantic interoperability, guidelines for a governance model related to a Service Catalogue are included as well.

CCS CONCEPTS

Network design principles, Cooperating communicating processes, Interoperability and Software usability.

KEYWORDS

Data Space, Service Catalogue, ZeroW, DSSC, Gaia-X, IDSA, Governance model.

1 Introduction

A Service Catalogue is a core function for federated, open data infrastructures, such as data spaces. It enables publication and discovery of services in a data space by means of Service Self-Descriptions [1][2]. The design and implementation of a data space Service Catalogue is described within the context of the EU project ZeroW [3], based on (upcoming) European standards. This paper addresses (i.) identification and mapping of available services that are offered by partners within the ZeroW project), (ii.) specification and design of the required functionality for creating and managing Service Catalogue entries, (iii.) publication and discovery functionalities of the Service Catalogue, and (iv.) metadata standards for describing services with Self-Descriptions, by using ontologies and semantic standards. Sharing of information whether it concerns static, dynamic or meta data, requires some form of control which is described in a Governance model of a data space. Therefore this paper also pays attention to

the organizational interoperability aspect not only for the duration of the project but also to provide a sustainable solution afterwards.

1.1 Background and related work

A Service Catalogue plays a crucial role in organizing and managing Self-Descriptions of services and data in federated, open data infrastructures, such as a Data Space. In Gaia-X, these Self-Descriptions contain information given by data space participants about themselves and their offered services [4]. A Service Catalogue enables publication of Self-Descriptions by providers and the discovery of Self-Descriptions by consumers, allowing them to select relevant Providers and their Service Offerings within a Data Space. The ZeroW project focuses on the reduction of food loss and waste via innovative solutions which also require an easy but controlled and secure way of sharing information with involved companies. Each of these companies offer business services in one or more agriculture, transport logistics and retail domains. A data space as technical solution for the required IT infrastructure fulfills a direct need including the publication and discovery function of a Service Catalogue.

2 Method

During the summer of 2023, the 6th Gaia-X hackathon has been organized in Bilbao (Spain) [5]. The focus of this hackathon has been on real-life end-to-end scenarios to leverage the Gaia-X (open source) software. One goal of this hackathon has been alignment and consolidation regarding the interpretation of the Gaia-X software specifications [4]. The results of that alignment has been used to design and then implement a Service Catalogue for the ZeroW project, thereby putting the (theoretical) specifications to the test in an actual implementation. For an actual implementation also rules and agreements have been identified and made to specify the expectations and obligations of the participants of the ZeroW data space for a Service Catalogue. The insights from the ZeroW implementation are described as governance guidelines in this paper. However, it is expected that the Governance model for the ZeroW project will be updated and extended based because the project is still on-going.

2.1 Research questions

Two research objectives have been the subject of this paper. The primary goal of the work is the realization of a Service Catalogue for the ZeroW project, based on the Gaia-X [1] and IDS [2] specifications. The experimental and investigative nature of this work explored the following question: “is it possible to realize a practical and useful implementation of a ZeroW service catalogue based on the current IDS and Gaia-X specifications?” The terms “practical” and “useful” referred to -in this case- the actual usability of the service catalogue by Service Providers, where these Providers could make use of an intuitive user interface and would not require any knowledge of the underlying technology of the Service Catalogue.

The second research question is supportive to the first one and has been formulated as: “which organizational interoperability aspects must be taken in account for an operational Service Catalogue?” Practically this means to identify the required addition to the governance model to describe which processes and responsibilities need to be in place before the software can do its work.

A third research question is not addressed in this paper but might be included in a follow-up paper or an update of this one because the ZeroW project is still going on. “How to implement a domain specific ontology in combination with the domain independent standards and frameworks such as Gaia-X[1] and IDS[2]?” Both standards support a layered approach by design but the implementation of a domain specific ontology such as the foreseen Agriculture Information Model (AIM)[9] requires still further research and development.

3 Artifact

The design of the ZeroW Service Catalogue is based on the Gaia-X Trust Framework [4]. In this framework, all participants, services and resources in a data space are represented by Self-Descriptions according to a common standard.

A Participant Self-Description contains information that is specific to a certain participant, such as their legal registration number, address and so on.

Services are described as *Service Offerings* that contain information about its terms and conditions, the data protection regime it falls under, and so forth. A Service Offering is always linked to a Participant Self-Description.

Resources can relate either to a physical or virtual (i.e. software or data) Resource, and one or multiple resources may be aggregated into a *Service Offering* (though a resource may exist independently of any Service Offering).

All above Self-Descriptions are stored inside the Service Catalogue, which is a central component within a data space. The Service Catalogue has search and discovery functionalities, so that all services within the data space can be found by potential consumers. Using Self-Descriptions based on the Gaia-X Trust

Framework as a common metadata standard for data spaces allows federation of a Service Catalogue across data spaces, which enables participants of one data space to search for services in other data spaces.

Please note that the actual consumption of services across data spaces requires interoperability not only at the catalogue level, but also at the level of Identity, Access Management and the Connector for the actual data exchange. The technical realization is out of scope of the paper but is taken in account regarding the require organizational / governance aspects

3.1 First implementation

The first implementation of the idea behind the Service Catalogue was realized during a hackathon that was organized by Gaia-X AISBL in May 2023 [5]. One track of this hackathon focused on creating a Data Product Passport with European Manufacturing & Gaia-X standards. The goal of this track was to capture the carbon footprint of the entire supply chain for a given product. This use case illustrated how data services, defined in Self-Descriptions, could be used to integrate data from different parties. and that they could be used for other purposes as well. This is the idea behind the Service Catalog for the ZeroW project.

Figure 1 shows the ZeroW Service Catalogue in a data space. The first implementation used two Connectors for simplification (an actual Data Space could potentially include a multitude of these types of Connectors). Each Connector offered a Service that was described in a Service Offering according to the Gaia-X Trust Framework.

Figure 1: the Service Catalogue of the ZeroW dataspace.

As can be seen in Figure 2, each Connector had its own Service Offering (Service SD in the picture), which consisted of the Self-Description of the service itself, the Participant Self-Description and the Self-Description of the Connector. Identification was based on the fact that each Service Offering was linked to a Participant Self-Description, which was verified by the Gaia-X Digital Clearing House to be a valid Participant. Furthermore, the identity of each Connector had already been verified by the Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service in the IDS ecosystem. Therefore, it was known that the Participant was part of the ZeroW Dataspace.

Figure 2: The layered structure of the Service Self Descriptions.

This service catalog, based on service offerings of the participants and services in the ZeroW Dataspace can be of great help for all the SILLs that are in this project. Because the metadata is described in a uniform way, the service catalogue could also be federated towards other data spaces in other domains. This enables participants of the ZeroW dataspace to obtain data from other data spaces, or offer their services to participants of other data spaces.

Furthermore, the focus of the ZeroW catalogue is to give a simple, yet complete summary of the Service Offerings. The focus on simplicity is to enable the benefits of Data Spaces to people who have little to no knowledge about it. The ZeroW Catalogue takes only the name of the Service, the URL and the description and from this creates a Service Offering. This means that for both viewing all the services that are available and the addition of new services are doable for people without specific knowledge about Gaia-X credentials, data spaces, etc.

3.2 Governance guidelines

A Service Catalogue enables discovery of services by facilitating *publication of self-descriptions* and *search capabilities*. The terms and conditions for self-descriptions including mandatory content is stated in the governance model of a data space. This includes the definition of terminology to enable semantic interoperability by including a reference to the semantic model that is used to describe a *service*. For the ZeroW project, the information objects relevant for governance of a Service Catalogue are identified and visualized in the figure 3. A verifiable *service identification* and a verifiable *service certification* contribute to the trust aspect. The Governance model describes the Identification and Authentication process including which (trusted) organization who can perform them, also known as Trust-anchors. A Certification Scheme is also part of the governance model and describes for each type of

service what level of certification is required and what the focus of the certification is. The result of a successful certification process is a digital certificate which can be verified by the Evaluating issuer and be used by the connector as authorization discriminator.

Figure 3: conceptual model for a service description (offering)

The terms and conditions for using a service as described in the *services conditions* as well the *capabilities of a service* can be used to determine which services are applicable. The service conditions must be compliant with the governance model of the providing dataspace. Within the ZeroW dataspace, participants can use self-sovereign identities validated by a Trust-anchor and must digitally sign to comply with the Governance model before they become a “trusted” participant. The semantic model used by the service as well to describe the IT services in the Service catalogue is stated in the Governance model by referring to standards such as DCAT, Gaia-X Self-descriptions and a domain specific ontology. A *domain specific ontology* is not implemented yet but required to specify in a uniform way the functional capabilities of a service. When a suitable service has been found, agreements about usage have to be made with the *accountable organization* that is providing the service. Defining a service contract and the operational use of a service are outside the scope of a Service Catalogue. Finally the *connectivity information* contains the required network information to address the service.

A service catalogue has a service description of its own and contains also the service descriptions of other published services. The *service conditions* for the ZeroW Service Catalogue are currently only limited by the terms and conditions as stated in the ZeroW Governance model. Within the ZeroW project, only partners of the ZeroW project are allowed to publish services at the Service Catalogue until the governance organization decides otherwise and changes the governance model. In general the use of the search capabilities of a Service Catalogue from outside a data space is possible as long as the external users agree to be compliant with the *service conditions* of the catalogue and the *governance model* of the providing dataspace. One important requirement will be agreement about mutually trusted Certification and Trust-anchors. In other words, only users with a

verifiable identification provided by accepted Trust-anchors can use the ZeroW Service Catalogue via the ZeroW Service Catalogue website or via an API with use of a trusted (certified) external service.

Since discovery is a core function of a data space, the Service Catalogue needs to be hosted by an organization trusted by all participants of the dataspace. This is also applicable for the identification and authentication functions provided by Trust anchors, as well for certification of services provided by Evaluation authorities. The provider of the Services Catalogue is also accountable for compliance with the Governance model and for monitoring the security, integrity and privacy aspects of the service. Especially in view of the increasing attention and need for Cybersecurity measures to prevent deception and abuse.

In other words, a Service Catalogue (and services in general) can be used by an internal/external users if their identity can be verified, and they comply with terms and conditions of that service and the Governance model. This requires common Trust-anchors, Certified services and a common vocabulary for proper interpretation of the terms and conditions.

4 Discussion

The results of the current study showed that it is technically feasible to create a Service Catalogue based on the Gaia-X Trust Framework architecture, which was demonstrated by creating and implementing a Service Catalogue for the ZeroW Data Space.

The architecture of the ZeroW Service Catalogue showed that identities are verified twice: once by the Gaia-X Clearing House and once by the Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service. In the architecture around the new Data Space protocol, the connector as it is right now will change drastically [7]. With this change, we foresee a shift in the world of Data Spaces away from the Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service and more towards a decentralized form of authentication, where identities in Data Spaces will move towards Verifiable Credentials [8]. This fits perfectly into the Self-Descriptions of Participants in Gaia-X. Therefore, with this new protocol, the duplication in identity verification, as mentioned in the implementation section 3.1, will disappear, and only one single method of identification will remain.

The current implementation of the Service Catalogue could be federated to other data spaces, because of the uniform and standardized way of describing services according to the Gaia-X Trust Framework [4]. However, the current implementation was not yet equipped with a vocabulary to ensure Semantic Interoperability. Future work should aim to investigate how to improve this Semantic Interoperability by extending the semantic model for ZeroW and the agri-sector, in compliance with the Agriculture Information Model [9]. Also automated support to verify compliancy of terms and conditions for services and data spaces will make it easier to determine if services can be used or which additional measures have to be taken to become compliant.

However the use of a common semantic model to describe the terms and conditions is expected as a practical requirement to enable such feature to lower the risk of misinterpretations.

5 Conclusion

In the context of ZeroW, federated data-services is about sharing information between decentralized services where the information can be requested at one service while the data itself can be stored distributed across one or more other federating services. A federated service is a verifiable and trusted IT-service of the ZeroW dataspace. There are two high level requirements defined to become a trusted IT-service: comply to the terms and conditions as agreed in the Governance model for identification of the providing organization (applicant) and the certification of the service itself.

A first version of a Service Catalogue has been created with verifiable participants and service self-descriptions based on DCAT and Gaia-X Self-Descriptions standards. These standards lower the technical and semantic interoperability barrier to enable federation within and between data spaces. Verification of claims is handled by the ZeroW dataspace using trust anchors and verifiable certificates. Without any knowledge about these standards, participants can add and maintain the meta-information about services via a simple web form. A conceptual service model defines the minimum required information elements to support the underlying trust framework and governance model. A Service Catalogue is an intermediate feature of a data space and therefore the terms and conditions for usage are part of the governance model of that data space.

The Service Catalogue can be extended with a domain-specific semantic model to increase correct interpretation of the capabilities, terms and conditions for published services. In the case of the ZeroW project, the Agriculture Information Model (AIM)[9] is chosen to increase the semantic interoperability, but the application of that model requires further research and development.

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